

Automated Text Summarization using NLP

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Abstract—This study explores automated book Summarization using Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Python-Flask. The aim is to provide a concise yet comprehensive overview of a book's content. Leveraging NLP algorithms for feature extraction and semantic analysis, the system condenses key information. The implementation in Python-Flask ensures user-friendly accessibility. This approach addresses the escalating volume of digital content, offering a practical solution for quick comprehension. The synthesis of NLP and Python-Flask presents a versatile tool for readers and researchers, showcasing the potential of automated text Summarization in streamlining information retrieval and enhancing overall accessibility

Keywords—Automated Summarization, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

In the age of information overload, the ability to distill extensive textual content into concise and accessible summaries has become imperative. By combining the potent tools of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and the adaptable Python-Flask framework, this course explores the developing topic of automated book Summarization. The main goal is to use feature extraction and semantic analysis tools provided by NLP algorithms to build a system that can effectively condense essential knowledge from books.

The use of NLP is essential for unraveling the many intricacies of language and enabling the system to understand the main ideas of the text. The cornerstone is featuring extraction, which sifts through the textual environment to pinpoint and rank crucial components that significantly advance the plot of the book. On the other hand, semantic analysis gives the system the ability to comprehend the contextual connections between words and phrases, ensuring that the summaries that are produced not only capture the substance but also preserve coherence.

This automated Summarization system's integration into the Python-Flask framework was purposefully chosen. In addition to facilitating smooth integration with the Summarization model, Python-Flask, which is renowned for its simplicity and scalability, also offers a user-friendly experience. The combination of NLP and Python-Flask emerges as a useful option for the quick comprehension of dense textual information in an era where digital content is seeing an unheard-of boom.

This session seeks to explore the mutually beneficial relationship between Python-Flask and NLP, demonstrating how useful and productive they can be together. This synthesis has the potential to improve accessibility across the board in the digital environment by not only fulfilling readers' immediate requirements but also giving researchers a more efficient method of information retrieval

II. RELATED WORK

A. "Automatic Short Text Summarization Techniques in Social Media"

This study examines how new developments in Natural Language Processing (NLP) are used to summarize short texts on social media. The study's objective is to distill and extract valuable information from condensed social media texts. To accomplish effective Summarization, the authors explore numerous NLP strategies, adding to the field of text analysis in social media situations.

B. "Survey on Automatic Text Summarization using NLP and Deep Learning"

In this ground-breaking work, the authors provide a semantic extractive text Summarization approach, deftly tackling the dilemma of keeping crucial information while removing redundant and irrelevant content, considerably increasing the Summarization process.

C. "Text Summarization of Amazon Customer Reviews using NLP"

This paper introduces an innovative approach to text Summarization using NLP, leveraging semantic analysis. The proposed method optimizes the Summarization process by considering the semantic structure of the text, achieving more accurate and contextually relevant summaries

D. "Text Summarization using Secretary problem"

Unattended text Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) both depend on Summarization. Using the Secretary problem, which splits the document text into two sections, a novel idea is put forth to construct a summary. The best candidate will be identified one-third of the time using this procedure, which compares primary headings and sentences.

E. "Unsupervised Machine Learning Approach for

“Extractive Punjabi Text Summarization”

Natural Language Processing (NLP)'s core function of text Summarization is the extraction of meaningful information from text. This study provides an unsupervised machine learning-based Punjabi Extractive Text Summarize. Tokenization, stop word removal, similarity matrix construction, rating, and summary production are all features of the system. The system was assessed using ROGUE scores, with 0.71, 0.56, and 0.56 being the highest values.

III. METHODOLOGY

The approach for text Summarization is using SpaCy is an open-source natural language processing (NLP) library for Python as follows:

A. Text Preprocessing:

Text preprocessing in extractive Summarization involves cleaning the raw text data. This includes removing stop words, punctuation, and irrelevant characters. The goal is to ensure that the remaining content is meaningful and relevant for further analysis.

B. Sentence Tokenization:

Sentence tokenization is the process of breaking down the text into individual sentences. This step is crucial for extractive Summarization as it forms the basis for identifying important sentences that will be included in the summary.

C. Sentence Scoring

In extractive Summarization, each sentence is assigned a score based on various features such as word frequency, importance of terms, and position in the document. Sentence scoring aims to quantify the significance of each sentence in the context of the entire document.

D. Ranking Sentences:

Once sentences are scored, they are ranked in descending order based on their importance scores. Higher-ranked sentences are considered more critical and are more likely to be included in the final summary.

E. Selecting Top Sentences

The final step involves selecting a predefined number of top-ranked sentences to construct the extractive summary. These sentences collectively represent the most important information from the original document, providing a concise overview.

IV. BUILD MODEL

For building a reliable and accurate machine learning model for the successful text extraction, as follow the following steps

A. Importing Libraries

```
import spacy
from spacy.lang.en.stop_words import STOP_WORDS
from string import punctuation
from heapq import nlargest
```

1) import spacy:

This line imports the spaCy library, which is a powerful and widely used natural language processing (NLP) library in Python. It is used to leverage spaCy's functionalities for tasks such as tokenization, part-of-speech tagging, and sentence segmentation.

2) From spacy.lang.en.stop_words import STOP_WORDS:

Imports the set of stop words from spaCy's English language model. Stop words are common words (e.g., "the," "and," "is") that are often excluded in NLP tasks to focus on the more meaningful content. In this code, it is used to filter out stop words from the text.

3) from string import punctuation

Imports a set of common punctuation marks. This is used for further text preprocessing. Punctuation characters are commonly not needed in text summarization tasks, as they do not contribute much to the meaning. This set is later used to filter out punctuation from the text.

4) from heapq import nlargest

Imports the nlargest function from the heapq module. The nlargest function is used to efficiently select the top sentences based on their scores. In this code, it is applied to get the most important sentences for creating the summary

B. Preprocessing Text:

The code loads the English language model from spaCy, tokenizes the input text, and removes stop words.

```
stopwords = list(STOP_WORDS)
nlp = spacy.load('en_core_web_sm')
doc = nlp(text)
tokens = [token.text for token in doc]
```

C. Word Frequency Calculation:

```
word_frequencies = {}
for word in doc:
    if word.text.lower() not in stopwords:
        if word.text.lower() not in punctuation:
            if word.text not in word_frequencies.keys():
                word_frequencies[word.text] = 1
            else:
                word_frequencies[word.text] += 1
```

D. Normalize Word Frequencies:

```
max_frequency = max(word_frequencies.values())
for word in word_frequencies.keys():
    word_frequencies[word] = word_frequencies[word] / max_frequency
```

E. Sentence Tokenization:

```
sentence_tokens = [sent for sent in doc.sents]
print(sentence_tokens)
```

F. Calculate Sentence Scores:

```

sentence_scores = {}
for sent in sentence_tokens:
    for word in sent:
        if word.text.lower() in word_frequencies.keys():
            if sent not in sentence_scores.keys():
                sentence_scores[sent] = word_frequencies[word.text.lower()]
            else:
                sentence_scores[sent] += word_frequencies[word.text.lower()]
    
```

G. Selecting Top Sentences:

```

from heapq import nlargest
select_length = int(len(sentence_tokens) * 0.3)
summary = nlargest(select_length, sentence_scores, key=sentence_scores.get)
    
```

H. Combine Sentences for Summary:

```

final_summary = [word.text for word in summary]
summary = ' '.join(final_summary)
    
```

I. Result

Fig.1. Result displaying the summary 100 words

Fig.2. Result displaying the summary 700 words

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the application of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, particularly leveraging the spaCy library, holds immense promise in the field of text Summarization. Through the journey of exploring and implementing text Summarization, several key insights have emerged.

As an advanced NLP library, SpaCy provides solid functions that are essential for the various steps in the text summarizing process. SpaCy offers a strong framework for creating extractive Summarization systems, ranging from effective tokenization to sophisticated language analyses. By removing unhelpful components, the incorporation of spaCy's stop words and punctuation handling improves the precision of the Summarization.

The strategy taken to extractive Summarization in this study, which combines frequency analysis and sentence rating, is practical. The algorithm effectively finds and chooses the most important content for the summary by assigning importance ratings to sentences based on the frequency and relevance of terms. By using the NLargest technique, the top sentences are extracted even more quickly while maintaining an accurate representation of the original text.

Using spaCy to summarize text is more than just a technical exercise; it is a potent tool with practical uses. Long papers can be condensed into brief summaries, which has consequences for information retrieval and speeds up comprehension and decision-making. The effectiveness and precision shown by spaCy-powered Summarization, whether used to news stories, research papers, or any lengthy text, dramatically improve productivity and accessibility.

The future of automatic text Summarization is set to be significantly shaped by libraries like spaCy as NLP developments continue to take shape. The transformation of raw text into meaningful summaries demonstrates the potential of NLP to change how we interact with and get knowledge from large amounts of textual data. The

combination of spaCy's capabilities with cutting-edge methods promises to open new horizons in the field of text Summarization as the discipline develops, making information more palatable and usable for a variety of applications.

VI. REFERENCES

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